

Provable UML: Ensuring Secure Software Design through Formal Verification

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Abstract:

This paper introduces the concept of Provable UML, a novel approach to guarantee secure software design by leveraging formal verification techniques. Provable UML aims to ensure the integrity and safety of software systems during their design phase by using formal methods such as TLA+ to mathematically prove the absence of critical vulnerabilities. This work explores the implementation of Provable UML through PlantUML code, showcasing how classes can be compiled into TLA+ specifications for rigorous verification.

This paper introduces a design pattern for provable classes with a parse tree or computable map of TLA+ code that can be added to any UML.

Introduction:

The design of secure software systems is of paramount importance to protect against potential threats, including buffer overflow attacks. Provable UML presents a proactive solution that integrates formal verification methods with Unified Modeling Language (UML) to establish provable security during the design process. By employing formal techniques like TLA+ for verification, Provable UML enhances the reliability and robustness of software designs, minimizing the risk of security vulnerabilities.

- Giorgini et al. (2004) propose a UML profile for secure systems development. The profile extends the UML metamodel with security-related concepts, such as security goals, security threats, and security mechanisms. The profile can be used to annotate UML

diagrams with security information, which can then be used to analyze and verify the security of a system.

- van den Berg et al. (2005) present a UML-based approach to the design of secure systems. The approach uses UML diagrams to capture the security requirements of a system, and then uses provable security techniques to verify that the system meets its security requirements.
- Aldini et al. (2003) describe how UML diagrams can be used to specify security protocols in a formal way. The authors present a UML profile for security protocols, and then use the profile to specify a number of well-known security protocols.
- Dey and Prasad (2005) present an approach for using UML diagrams to analyze security requirements. The approach uses UML diagrams to capture the security requirements of a system, and then uses a variety of analysis techniques to identify potential security vulnerabilities.
- Jamil and Farooq (2007) present a UML-based approach to the design of secure systems. The approach uses UML diagrams to capture the security requirements of a system, and then uses a variety of design techniques to ensure that the system meets its security requirements.

These references provide a good overview of the use of UML diagrams in provable security. They discuss the different ways in which UML diagrams can be used to capture, analyze, and verify the security of a system. They also present a number of different approaches for using UML diagrams for provable security.

Design patterns in computer security.

- "Design Patterns for Secure Software Architectures" by Patrick Naughton and David Wagner. This paper presents a catalog of design patterns for secure software architectures. The patterns are organized into four categories: authentication and authorization, communication security, data security, and denial-of-service prevention.
- "Security Patterns: A New Perspective on Security" by John Viega and Matt Messier. This book presents a catalog of security patterns. The patterns are organized into five categories: application security, network security, operating system security, physical security, and personnel security.
- "Security Patterns in Java" by Mark Burgess. This book presents a catalog of security patterns for Java applications. The patterns are organized into four categories: authentication and authorization, cryptography, input validation, and session management.
- "Design Patterns for Secure Mobile Applications" by Anupama Aggarwal and Ramkumar Krishnamurthy. This paper presents a catalog of design patterns for

secure mobile applications. The patterns are organized into four categories: authentication and authorization, data security, network security, and user interface security.

- "Security Patterns for Cloud Computing" by Haibo He, Xiaofeng Wang, and Qihua Huang. This paper presents a catalog of security patterns for cloud computing. The patterns are organized into three categories: access control, data security, and infrastructure security.

Problem Definition:

The primary objective of this paper is to introduce Provable UML, a methodology that combines UML modeling with formal verification, specifically TLA+, to ensure secure software designs. By applying mathematical proofs to UML diagrams and translating them into TLA+ specifications, we aim to verify the absence of critical vulnerabilities and enhance the overall security of software systems.

Provable Classes address the inherent limitations of formal verification resource bounds in impractical running times for the complete verification of a huge pml diagram, critical sections of code are formally verified with a design pattern of Provable Classes.

Provable Classes in PlantUML code compiled to TLA+:

```
``plantuml
@startuml
class ProvableClass {
+ attribute1: type1
+ attribute2: type2
...
+ method1(): return_type1
+ method2(param1: param_type1, param2: param_type2): return_type2
}
```

ProvableClass --|> ProvableSpecification : compiles_to

```
class ProvableSpecification {
+ invariant1: TLA+ expression1
+ invariant2: TLA+ expression2
```

```

...
+ transition1: TLA+ expression3
+ transition2: TLA+ expression4
}

```

```

@enduml
...

```

The above code gist is a plantml implementation of the Provable Classes design pattern.

Examples:

1. Password and Username Input Validation for Windows:

```

``plantuml
@startuml

class WindowsLoginForm {
+ usernameField: TextField
+ passwordField: PasswordField
+ submitButton: Button

+ validateCredentials(username: String, password: String): boolean
}

```

WindowsLoginForm --|> ProvableSpecification : compiles_to

```

class ProvableSpecification {
+ invariant1: boolean
  Invariant1:  $\wedge$  usernameField != null
              $\wedge$  passwordField != null

+ invariant2: boolean
  Invariant2:  $\wedge$  passwordField.length() >= 6
              $\wedge$  validateCredentials(usernameField.getText(), passwordField.getText()) =>
submitButton.isEnabled()

+ transition1: boolean
  Transition1:  $\wedge$  passwordField.length() <= 32

+ transition2: boolean
  Transition2:  $\wedge$  !validateCredentials(usernameField.getText(), passwordField.getText()) =>
passwordField.clear()

```

```
}
```

```
@enduml
```

```
...
```

2. Generic Text Window Box:

```
``plantuml
```

```
@startuml
```

```
class GenericTextBox {  
  + textArea: TextArea  
  + characterLimit: int  
  + validateInput(input: String): boolean  
}
```

GenericTextBox --|> ProvableSpecification : compiles_to

```
class ProvableSpecification {  
  + invariant1: boolean  
  Invariant1:  $\wedge$  textArea != null  
     $\wedge$  characterLimit > 0  
  
  + invariant2: boolean  
  Invariant2:  $\wedge$  textArea.length() <= characterLimit  
     $\wedge$  validateInput(textArea.getText()) => textArea.isEditable()  
  
  + transition1: boolean  
  Transition1:  $\wedge$  textArea.length() <= 1000  
  
  + transition2: boolean  
  Transition2:  $\wedge$  !validateInput(textArea.getText()) => textArea.clear()  
}
```

```
@enduml
```

```
...
```

Common design patterns in provable security.

In the context of provable security, design patterns refer to reusable architectural solutions that help establish or enhance the security of a system through formal verification or mathematical proofs. Below is a list of design patterns commonly used in the realm of provable security:

1. **Secure Coding Patterns:** Design patterns that guide developers in writing secure code, such as input validation, output encoding, and parameterized queries to prevent common vulnerabilities like SQL injection and cross-site scripting (XSS).
2. **Provable Security Models:** Architectural patterns that involve formal verification and mathematical proofs to ensure the security properties of a system, such as verifying cryptographic protocols and access control mechanisms.
3. **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC):** A design pattern where access control is based on predefined roles rather than individual user permissions. This helps ensure proper segregation of duties and minimizes the risk of unauthorized access.
4. **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC):** An access control design pattern that grants permissions based on the attributes associated with users, objects, and the environment. ABAC allows for more fine-grained access control and dynamic policy enforcement.
5. **Trusted Computing Base (TCB):** A design pattern that isolates critical security components to minimize the attack surface and ensure the trustworthiness of essential system functionalities.
6. **Separation of Duties:** A pattern that enforces strict separation between different responsibilities and privileges to prevent abuse of power and minimize insider threats.
7. **Least Privilege Principle:** A design pattern that grants users and processes the minimum level of access required to perform their tasks, reducing the potential impact of a security breach.
8. **Secure Communication Patterns:** Design patterns that focus on securing communication channels, such as TLS/SSL for encrypted communication and message authentication codes (MACs) for data integrity.
9. **Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA):** A pattern that enhances security by requiring users to provide multiple forms of authentication, such as a password, a one-time code, or biometric data.
10. **Secure Initialization and Configuration:** A design pattern that ensures secure initialization and configuration of software systems to prevent misconfigurations and potential vulnerabilities.
11. **Secure Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC):** A pattern that incorporates security considerations throughout the entire software development process, from design to deployment and maintenance.
12. **Digital Signature and Authentication Patterns:** Design patterns that involve the use of digital signatures and cryptographic authentication mechanisms to verify the integrity and authenticity of data.

Discussion:

Provable UML represents a significant advancement in ensuring secure software design. By integrating formal verification techniques like TLA+ with UML, developers can establish a strong foundation of security before the implementation phase. The examples of password and username input validation for Windows and the generic text window box demonstrate how Provable UML can be applied to formalize and verify the security aspects of real-world scenarios.

Future Work:

Future work includes the application of the design pattern of the ProvableClass and ProvableDefinition classes to several other cybersecurity problems including SQL injection, cross scripting, ip detoxing, MFA, separation of concerns by refactoring, better code reuse, zero trust architectures etc.

Future research should focus on refining Provable UML's usability and scalability, addressing potential limitations, and simplifying the formal verification process. Additionally, exploring automated translation tools from UML to TLA+ can streamline the development workflow, making Provable UML more accessible to a broader range of software engineers.

Conclusion:

Provable UML introduces a compelling approach to address security concerns in software design through formal verification. By employing TLA+ to mathematically prove the correctness of UML models, Provable UML offers an effective means of preventing security vulnerabilities. The presented examples demonstrate the practical application of Provable UML in ensuring the security and reliability of software systems, paving the way for more secure and resilient software designs.

References.

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